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A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON IMPACT OF GST ON INDIAN TEXTILE INDUSTRY**A. Benazir ¹****Dr. S. Archanabai ²****Abstract**

GST stands for Goods and Services Tax, which is applied on goods and services at a national level for achieving overall economic growth of a country. GST is designed to replace the indirect taxes imposed on goods and services by the Central and States. GST bill was officially introduced in the year 2014. But GST was passed by the Parliament on 8 August 2016, followed by ratification of the bill by more than 15 states and enactment of the bill in early September 2016 and GST is implemented from 1st July 2017. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is the biggest and most significant tax reform in India. The tax rate has become a blessing for some sectors of Indian textile industry, at the same time; it has become a burden for some sectors, especially for the people related to unorganized business segment. Textile sector of India is one of the top contributors toward the development of the Indian economy. Textile Industry is one of the oldest manufacturing industries in the country and the second largest industry, after agriculture. The textile industry employs both skilled and unskilled people. This paper is an analysis of impact of GST on textile sector. However, the impact of GST on the textile sector will be quite important. Taxation of textile sector is presently opaque and non-neutral across its various segments. This study examines the implications of GST for the Indian textile industry.

Keywords: GST, Impact on Export and Import, Future of Textile Industry

Introduction

Textile sector of India is one of the top contributors toward the development of the Indian economy. It is one of the oldest manufacturing industries in the country and the second largest industry, after agriculture. The textile industry employs both skilled and unskilled people. The industry contributes over 10 percent of the total annual exports of the country.

The textile industry has two segments, organised and unorganised. The unorganised textile sector includes handicraft, handloom, small and medium scale mills whereas an organised sector consists of spinning, garment and apparel which uses modern machinery and techniques. Under the GST, the rate structure for textile is decided at 5% for cotton fiber and 18% for manmade synthetic fiber while silk and jute are totally exempted from the same. The GST council has mentioned some rules regarding the e-way bill and rates. At the same time, the GST rates on job work of textiles and the related products that are manufactured are reduced from 18% to

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5%. With the implementation of GST, the difficulties in the textile sector have been eased out.

Benefits of GST

A. To Textile Industry: -

- It ensures easy compliance and Transparent
- It establishes uniformity of tax rates and structures
- It helps in removal of cascading
- It helps to improve competitiveness

B. To Central and State Governments: -

- It is Simple and easy to administer
- It has a better control on leakage
- It gives higher revenue efficiency

C. To consumers

- It is a single and transparent tax proportionate to the value of goods and services.
- It provides relief in overall tax burden:

Review of literature

Shefali (2016) studied "A Research Paper on an Impact of Goods and Services Tax (GST) on Indian Economy" and found that GST will simplify existing indirect tax system and will help to remove inefficiencies created by the existing current heterogeneous taxation system only if there is a clear consensus over issues of threshold limit, revenue rate, and inclusion of petroleum products, electricity, liquor and real estate. Until the consensus is reached, the government should resist from implementing such regime.

Lourdunathan and Xavier (2017) studied "A study on implementation of goods and services tax (GST) in India: Prospectus and challenges" and concluded that GST will bring One Nation and One Tax market. Efficient formulation of GST will lead to resource and revenue gain for both Centre and States majorly through widening of tax base and improvement in tax compliance. She suggested in her research paper that it is necessary on the part of the government to educate, conduct proper training, continuous seminars and workshop on GST is need of the hour. Thus, necessary steps should be taken.

Jyotsna Oberoi (2017) studied "GST -A game changer for the textile sector in India" and concluded that introduction of GST will usher in a plethora of changes in the textile business of India with an overall positive impact on the sector. GST implementation is expected to produce impetus to various reforms and policy measures envisaged by the Government for the ease of doing business and to usher India into a simple, transparent and tax friendly regime.

Objectives of the study

- To understand the concept of GST.
- To study the role of textile industry in the Indian economy.
- To examine the impact on textile sector under GST regime.

Research methodology

The researcher used an explorative analysis technique and get support of past literature from various journals, annual, reports, newspapers and magazines covering wide assortment of educational literature on Goods and Services Tax. In keeping with the objectives of the study, the analysis style is of descriptive in nature. Available secondary data was extensively used for this study.

GST rates for textile products:

Tax Free Textile Goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Raw silk and silk waste b) Wool, not carded or combed c) Gandhi Topi, National Flag d) Khadi Yarn e) Coconut or Coir fiber f) Jute fibers raw or processed but not spun
5% GST (Fibers and Yarns)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Silk yarn b) Yarn of wool or of animal hair c) Cotton yarn, other than khadi yarn d) Cotton sewing thread e) Vegetable fibers and yarns such as Flax, Hemp, Paper yarn f) Embroidery or Zari articles
5% GST with no refund of ITC accumulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Woven fabrics of Silk or Silk waste b) Fabrics Wool or of animal hair c) Cotton fabrics d) Fabrics of other vegetable textile fibers e) Fabrics of manmade textile filaments
Mix Bag (5% GST if Sale value below ₹ 1000, 12% GST sale value above ₹ 1000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Articles of apparel and clothing accessories knitted or crocheted b) Articles of apparel and clothing accessories not knitted or crocheted c) Blankets and travelling rugs d) Curtains (including drapes) and interior blinds; curtain or bed valances e) Other furnishing articles, such as Bedspreads Counterpanes, Napkins, Pillow case, Table cloth
12% GST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Wadding and felt of Textile materials whether impregnated, coated, covered or laminated b) Nonwovens

	c) Rubber threads and covered yarns d) Metalized yarns, imitation Zari yarns e) All Carpets and Floor Coverings including mats
18% GST (Fibres and Yarns)	a) Synthetic filament yarn such as Nylon, Polyester, Acrylic etc. b) Artificial filament yarn like Viscose rayon, Cup ammonium Rayon etc. c) Sewing thread of manmade filaments d) Synthetic or artificial staple fibers e) Synthetic or artificial filament tow

Impact of GST on textile industry

India is the second largest fiber producing country in the world in the FY 2015-16. This industry provides employment to more than 50 million people. It is a labor-intensive sector and also the largest contributing industry to the total export of India. The Implementation of GST will influence this prominent economic sector by revamping the existing indirect tax slabs. This study tries to bring out the impact of GST on Textile Industry of India.

➤ **Shifting towards an organized sector**

Large textile industries in the country work under the unorganized sector, therefore creating a gap between the flows of ITC. If a registered taxpayer procures the input from taxpayers under the composition scheme or the unorganised sector, ITC will not be allowed for him. Now with the implementation of GST, the input credit system smoothly shifts the balance toward the organised sector.

➤ **Reduction in manufacturing costs**

By subsuming the different taxes such as the entry tax, luxury tax, Octroi, etc., the costs for the manufacturers will be reduced in the textile industry.

➤ **Allowing input credit on capital goods**

The cost of import of the latest technology to manufacture textile goods is expensive. Because the excise duty paid for the same is not allowed at ITC. Under GST, however, ITC will be available for all the tax paid on capital goods.

➤ **Textile industry will be more competitive**

As per the Secretary of ITF (Indian Textpreneurs Federation) Prabhu Dhamodharan, GST will restructure the input tax credit claiming process. It will make the entire textile industry more aggressive in the export market

and it will also encourage the manufacturers to adopt cutting-edge production system to develop existing products. In addition to this, input tax credit will be an important step for promoting the export of textile products

➤ **GST will encourage the farmers**

Cotton yarn and fabrics will come under 5% GST tax slab and it will make the farmers to grow more amount of cotton than before. The farmers will get the reasonable price for their hard work.

➤ **Readymade garments will be costlier**

GST on readymade garments will create a huge difference in the current consumption. The tax slab will be 12% under GST while the present slab is 4-5% VAT and 2% excise. This higher tax slab will definitely increase the price of readymade garments for the consumers.

➤ **Developing Forward**

GST will bring vast changes in the textile industry of India. Man-made or synthetic fiber yarn will have 18%, readymade garments will have 12%, and cotton yarn and fabrics will come under 5% GST tax slab. Silk and jute will not have any indirect tax under GST. It will also improve the textile export scenario of India.

➤ **Job workers status under GST**

Under textile industry, processing of goods through job work is a normal phenomenon. Considering the labour intensive focus of job-work for textile products, the GST rate on job work on textile-related items has been reduced from 18% to 5%.

➤ **GST Impact on Exports**

The exports of readymade garment have declined by about 40 percent. This was mainly due to cut in duty drawbacks after GST implementation. Another major reason for this decline is the unavailability of GST refund to the exports industry manufacturers and suppliers, which has affected the cash flow in the industry resulting in a shortage of money. The export committee has formally requested the government to clear the pending credits and GST refund as soon as possible.

➤ **GST Impact on Imports of Textiles**

The import of textile is continuously growing during the last few months. GST has reduced the import duties and created a welcoming path for overseas fabric and garments into the country. Furthermore, the import of fabric, textile yarn, and made-up materials surged 12% continuously from year to year and it has reached to \$ 153.9 million.

Indian garments industry is positioned in front of tough competition from imported textile stuff, specifically the competition is arousing from Bangladesh because its production cost is cheap compared to India. This has made the textile industry to request the Government to surge import duty

on MMF fabric, cotton fabric, and MMF yarn by 15% in favour to save the local fabric, yarn, garment manufacturers from reduced import duty dilemma.

Conclusion

GST will simplify the current procedures by converging various complex indirect taxes into a unified platform; it will also improve the textile export scenario of India. The introduction of GST has resulted in removal of concessions/exemptions for the textile industry which saw outrages and protests by various associations and players in the textile industry. However, GST would help exporters. The cash dealing would significantly reduce. The unorganized industry would not be advantaged. The compliant would find their goods competitive and this protected sector would also join in contributing to tax in addition to employment etc. which was there even today. Stocking pre-GST would reduce in this industry. Smaller players whether in the textile processing, job workers, fabric manufacturers or garment units would have to bring in discipline in their recorded purchases and proper accounting which has not been strong in the past. There may be a few drawbacks for the textile industry due to the higher tax rate and removal of benefits under cotton value chain, but it is safe to say that GST will help this industry in the long run by getting more registered taxpayers under a well-regulated system.

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